

**Multi-Mode Feedback in Large
Writing Classrooms at Antonine
University (Beirut, Lebanon)
Presented by Nina Kang**

Multi-Mode Feedback in Writing Classrooms

<p>April 22, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Foundations of Assessment in Language Teaching / Principles of Metacognition</p>
<p>April 29, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Whole Class Feedback: Identifying Common Mistakes with a Focus on Grammar & Mechanics</p>
<p>May 6, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Peer Feedback: Targeted Tasks & Discussions</p>
<p>May 13, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Self Feedback: Showcasing Growth through Writing Portfolios & Projects</p>
<p>May 20, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Final Debriefing: Discussing Challenges & Best Practices</p>

Agenda, Session 2

Warm-Up & Review - 10min

Presentation w Discussion - 50min

Break - 5min

Small Group Activity (breakout room) – 30
min

Wrap up - 5min

Multi-Mode Feedback in Large Writing Classrooms

Workshop Objectives:

- Learn to identify student texts appropriate for modeling feedback on content, stylistic, and grammatical issues
- Introduce and practice using multi-mode feedback strategies
- Develop strategies aimed at helping students to construct their own criteria leading to self-corrections and other self-directed skills

Review: Concepts on Student Learning

Review

- Understanding importance of Feedback as a way to
- Mindset shift from traditional approach to marking student papers to providing feedback that targets learning

Motivation – appeal to both types

Extrinsic – external motivation; rewards driven; goal-orientation (grades, scores, achievement)

Intrinsic – internal motivation; autonomy and self-efficacy (sense of accomplishment, learning, growth; confidence)

Summative tasks & feedback

VS.

****FORMATIVE tasks & feedback****

Goal: TRANSFER OF KNOWLEDGE, i.e., the ability to evaluate & produce their own language ability

**Refer to Bloom's Taxonomy*

Bloom's Taxonomy

create

Produce new or original work

Design, assemble, construct, conjecture, develop, formulate, author, investigate

evaluate

Justify a stand or decision

appraise, argue, defend, judge, select, support, value, critique, weigh

analyze

Draw connections among ideas

differentiate, organize, relate, compare, contrast, distinguish, examine, experiment, question, test

apply

Use information in new situations

execute, implement, solve, use, demonstrate, interpret, operate, schedule, sketch

understand

Explain ideas or concepts

classify, describe, discuss, explain, identify, locate, recognize, report, select, translate

remember

Recall facts and basic concepts

define, duplicate, list, memorize, repeat, state

Part 1:
Basis for
Whole Class
Feedback

Whole Class Feedback (WCF)

True or False?

- Lots of written feedback on student's writing = high quality feedback
- WCF doesn't take a lot of time to prepare.

Effectiveness of WCF Key Findings

- Less time spent on grading papers (11-min per ss for individual comments vs 3-min per ss for WCG)
- Jump in ss scores higher for those that received WCF vs those that received individual feedback

FIGURE 1
MINUTES SPENT MARKING

	Minutes whole-class feedback (average per student)	Minutes individual feedback (average per student)
Work 1	3 (0.3)	8 (0.7)
Work 1	2 (0.2)	15 (1.25)
Work 3	3 (0.3)	14 (1.2)
Work 4	3 (0.3)	7 (0.6)
Average	2.75 (0.275)	11 (0.9375)

Source: Department for Education, 2014

What is Whole Class Feedback (WCF)?

- Giving general or targeted feedback to the whole class on a range of issues pertaining to student learning.
- Can be used to 1) *PRAISE students* for good work and 2) *IDENTIFY students* who need additional support.

WCF: Advantages

- Can alleviate teacher's workload
- Can be used to identify & address learning gaps
- Can be used with other methods of feedback

- **Using Exemplars** (but not perfect)
- **Being Consistent** (fairness in assessing/grading)
- **Providing Routine** (pattern of assessing and evaluating errors)

Dual Level
Approach: Whole
Class (in
combination with
Individual
Feedback)

WCF – targeted,
instructional,
generalizable

*Individual
Feedback* –
individualized,
catered, specific

Why Whole-Class Feedback, Part 1?

Timely

Detailed

Formative

Why
Whole-
Class
Feedback,
Part 2

Explicit Teaching (as opposed
to Identifying Errors)

Responsive Questioning

Live Modelling

Part 2: Selecting Student Text for WCF

The screenshot shows a web browser window with several tabs open. The active tab is titled "Lorem ipsum - Wikipedia". The address bar shows the URL "https://www Lorem ipsum". The main content of the page is titled "Lorem Ipsum" in a large, black, serif font. Below the title is a quote in Latin: "Neque porro quisquam est qui dolorem ipsum quia dolor sit amet, consectetur, adipisci velit..." followed by its English translation: "There is no one who loves pain itself, who seeks after it and wants to have it, simply because it is pain...".

Below the quote, there are two columns of text. The left column is titled "What is Lorem Ipsum?" and the right column is titled "Why do we use it?". Both columns contain text about the history and use of Lorem Ipsum. The text in the left column is partially obscured by a context menu that is open over the word "Lorem". The context menu includes options like "Copy", "Search Google for 'Lorem ipsum'", "Paste...", "Noncontiguous Text Selection", and "Inspect".

The text in the right column is also partially obscured by a context menu that is open over the word "ipsum". The context menu includes options like "Copy", "Search Google for 'Lorem ipsum'", "Paste...", "Noncontiguous Text Selection", and "Inspect".

Identifying Mistakes

1

Differentiate
between major and
minor mistake

2

Differentiate
between individual
and group errors

3

Track (instead of just
observing)

ALI245/255: Correction Symbols

SYMBOL		EXPLANATION	EXAMPLES
cs	Comma Splice	Connecting sentences with a comma	I like apples, sometimes I like oranges too.
frag	Fragment	Incomplete sentence	Because I like to eat. Boiling the water.
ro	Run-on	Sentence is too long	Homework was hard so I asked my sister to help me but she didn't want to because she was busy also with her homework that she had to finish.
ss	Sentence Structure	Incorrect sentence structure; rewrite the sentence	
rephrase/unclear	Rephrase/Unclear	Meaning is unclear; rewrite the sentence	
vb	Verb	Incorrect use of verb	I am have a lot of favorite food. Coffee lets me have a lot of energy.
vf	Verb Form	Incorrect verb ending	Mark was deeply influence by the book. I have meet many new people since I comed to America.
vt	Verb Tense	Incorrect verb tense	Yesterday I go home early because I was tired. I am born in Australia and I come to America last year.
mod	Modal	Incorrect use of modal	
parall	Parallelism		
pass	Passive	Incorrect use of the passive	I was helped my mother to prepare dinner.
prep	Preposition	Incorrect use of preposition	The mother gave the toy at the child.
wf	Word Form	Incorrect word ending	America people are very friendly and smile. /I didn't do anything all day. I am very boring. The movies was very excite and I really enjoyed it.
wc	Word Choice	Awkward choice of word	The soup tastes very wonderful. The soup has many things like onion, garlic, and pepper.
ww	Wrong Word	Wrong choice of word	Caffeine doesn't effect me.
wo	Word Order	Incorrect or awkward word order	I dance always on the weekend.
sv	Subject-Verb	Subject and verb must agree	She smoke too much but she always complain about other people who smokes in public.
pn	Pronoun	Wrong use of Pronoun	Even though I eat a lot, it doesn't make me gain weight. Sara hates it when her mother yells, so she just ignores her.
pn ref	Pronoun Reference	No or unclear pronoun reference	My mother and sister both enjoy classical music. She went to a concert last night. USC has a good engineering school. It is well-known throughout the world.
sing	Singular	Use the singular form	I eat a lot of fishes and vegetables.
pl	Plural	Use plural form	Jennifer hate the person who smoke.
cap	Capitalization	Capitalize letter	I traveled to france and italy last year.
lc	Lower Case	Use small case letter	The trip was GREAT! I really enjoy Traveling the World.
sp	Spelling	Wrong spelling	I have many frinds who support and encurege me.
art	Article	Incorrect or missing article	Last weekend, I bought new computer.
ab	Abbreviation	Spell out abbreviation	I live in LA, CA.
p	Punctuation	Wrong or missing punctuation	The ingredients include pepper and mushroom some beef and pork too.
^		Missing word or punctuation	

LEVEL 2 Errors: Less major / word level errors

LEVEL 3 Errors: Mechanics (including prepositions and articles)

1. Differentiate Major & Minor Errors

Whole Group Feedback - Simplified Template

Praise

This section can be used to share specific examples of what students have done well and to discuss what makes these examples effective so that a similar approach can be used by others next time. This is much more effective than using vague praise such as 'lots of good analysis'. Using ideas and examples from students' work in your class is also an opportunity to celebrate and show what is possible. This evidence of success by those in the same class can also be highly motivating

Model/Exemplar

The model or exemplar is ideally written together in lesson or live modelled by the teacher - this section is therefore left blank so that students can be shown the process. Alternatively, a pre-written model can be used from exam materials, students' work, or from a teacher model to exemplify the final outcome. This should be relatively short so that the teacher can focus on specific elements that have been done well and that can be practised and emulated by students. If using a pre-written model, this should be deconstructed and annotated in the lesson. Having the model on the same sheet also means this is easy to find and return to later.

Misconceptions

This could include common spelling errors or more substantive misconceptions such as those regarding plot, context or written expression. Having a separate section can more sharply focus our attention when giving feedback to help the teacher to specifically look out for misconceptions and address them which not only means these can be re-taught but may also influence decisions about how to teach this element next time.

Next Steps

Next steps should be precise and actionable, giving students an opportunity to improve their work by practising an element they did less well but also in allowing them to apply this to a new idea or piece of work. Students should only be given one or two clear next steps so that these can be deliberately practised and are not overwhelming. These next steps should be personalised based on their work so a student may just have '2' written on their work and know to complete Task 2. However, having these next steps visible to all students means they can all benefit from this advice.

Differentiate between
Individual and
Group Feedback

Source: Claire Hill,
Director of Secondary
Improvement

DISUSSION OF STUDENT SAMPLE (B1.2), 339 words

In Lebanon everything is different, so what can be better to university students in Lebanon ,online or on campus learning ? There is a big debate about this topic especially in Lebanon because of the country's situation and its impact on education. On campus learning is better for many reasons.

There are many reasons that gives preference to on campus learning over online learning in Lebanon for university students, one of them is that on campus, everyone can attend classes because it doesn't require internet unlike online learning where internet at home is essential. According to studies, 55% of Lebanese families after the crises are under the poverty level, so students have to work and miss classes to pay university and internet bills,without mentioning electricity crises .

Furthermore, on campus students can interact more with people , they can ask questions and get answered immediately so they can understand more , they also can have friends and build relationships , wich is so important to preserve a good mental health despite all the crises in Lebanon , while in online sessions, students are sitting hours in front of screens , they cant talk with anybody , and if they didn't understand they just leave the meeting.

There is one reason that makes online learning better than on campus learning, is the price of petrol in Lebanon. Recently , petrol tank in Lebanon costs 500 000 L.L , so students who lives far from the university will face a real issue especially with the current economic crisis unlike online learning where students can attend classes from their homes . But this can be fixed by taking a dorm in the university so they can reach it by walking.

In conclusion , on campus learning is better than online because everyone can attend sessions,students can build communities,and they can understand more.Even though in Lebanon everything seems like there is not a promising future but students should believe that they are the true revolution and with education they can change everything .

Individual Feedback (Turnitin)

In Lebanon, everything is different, so what can be better to university students in Lebanon, online or on campus learning? There is a big debate about this topic especially in Lebanon because of the country's situation and its impact on education. On campus learning is better for many reasons.

There are many reasons that gives preference to on campus learning over online learning in Lebanon for university students, one of them is that on campus, everyone can attend classes because it doesn't require internet unlike online learning where internet at home is essential. According to studies, 55% of Lebanese families after the crises are under the poverty level, so students have to work and miss classes to pay university and internet bills, without mentioning electricity crises.

6 minutes (127 words)

WCF, Approach 1

Identify the grammatical errors and make necessary corrections.

Furthermore, on campus students can interact more with people , they can ask questions and get answered immediately so they can understand more , they also can have friends and build relationships , wich is so important to preserve a good mental health despite all the crises in Lebanon , while in online sessions, students are sitting hours in front of screens , they cant talk with anybody , and if they didn't understand they just leave the meeting.

WCF, Approach 2

Identify the grammatical errors and make necessary corrections.

Furthermore, on campus students can interact more with people , they can ask questions and get answered immediately so they can understand more , they also can have friends and build relationships , wich is so important to preserve a good mental health despite all the crises in Lebanon , while in online sessions, students are sitting hours in front of screens , they cant talk with anybody , and if they didn't understand they just leave the meeting.

WCF, Approach 3

The following passage is a RUN-ON with multiple COMMA SPLICES. Fix the errors and rewrite the passage in 3-5 sentences.

Furthermore, on campus students can interact more with people , they can ask questions and get answered immediately so they can understand more , they also can have friends and build relationships , wich is so important to preserve a good mental health despite all the crises in Lebanon , while in online sessions, students are sitting hours in front of screens , they cant talk with anybody , and if they didn't understand they just leave the meeting.

WCF, Approach 4

Identify all the verbs (including auxiliaries) in the passage. Note all the repetitions and errors (e.g., verb tense, passive voice). Try rewriting to improve the passage.

Furthermore, on campus students can interact more with people , they can ask questions and get answered immediately so they can understand more , they also can have friends and build relationships , wich is so important to preserve a good mental health despite all the crises in Lebanon , while in online sessions, students are sitting hours in front of screens , they cant talk with anybody , and if they didn't understand they just leave the meeting.

WCF, Approach 5

Edit the following passage.

Furthermore, on campus students can interact more with people by asking questions and getting answers immediately, so they can understand more. They also can **have friends** and build **relationships** , **wich** is so important to preserve a good mental health despite all the crises in Lebanon. In online sessions, students **are sitting hours** in front of screens. They **cant** talk with **anybody** , and if they don't **understand they** just leave the meeting.

Discussion of a student sample:
What kind of WCF can we offer in the following case?

In this picture, there was a mother preparing food for her childrens, and she was very happy with her childrens. And the two childrens drinks juice before eating fishes. And, the dad is very happy with his happy family after a long day of work. (A2.2)

Summary Points

- WCF can be especially useful for targeted grammar and mechanics related lessons
- Apply WCF in conjunction (DUAL Approach) with other feedback strategies

Part 3:
Application
(Small Group
Activity)

Small Group Activity

1

Break out into 4 groups according to level (A1, B1.1, B1.2, B1.3).

2

Each group will be given a student sample to evaluate.

3

Brainstorm ideas on how you would provide WCF? (15min)

4

Be prepared to share 2-3 ideas with the rest of the group.

ANY
QUESTIONS?
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